

CITIZEN-SDSS PROJECT: Guidelines for conducting co-design scenario workshops in the Philippines

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1 Background CITIZEN-SDSS Project

The remaining Philippine forest landscapes cover around 24% of the country's total land area. These landscapes are characterised by a high level of endemism, yet they are simultaneously threatened by deforestation and forest degradation, which has long-lasting effects on the ecosystem services they provide to society. Nature-based solutions (NBS) encompass a wide range of measures, such as forest conservation, reforestation, and restoration, and can support local livelihoods through community woodlots, agroforestry, and other initiatives, including living fences and riverbank vegetation. NBS have the potential to safeguard the Philippines' remaining forest landscapes and support national wood demand, which is currently met by industrial timber plantations and imports.

The CITIZEN-SDSS project aims to inform decision-making to support the development of long-term land use and forest management strategies that utilise nature-based solutions to sustain local livelihoods and ecosystem services. The project focuses on four study sites and their surrounding provinces - see for further details on study landscape: Asare and Lippe (2025). The project combines participatory approaches and various forms of stakeholder interaction, such as key informant interviews, household interviews and focus group discussions, with geographic information systems (GIS) and spatiotemporal modelling. The latter can also be referred to as spatial decision support systems (SDSS). The project develops methodological approaches to make projections on long-term sustainable forest and land use management pathways, supporting local livelihoods and fostering nature-based solutions at Barangay level. This is important because decision-making processes require context-sensitive approaches that are also grounded in scientific rigour.

2 Objective of Co-design scenario workshops

This document provides guidance on how to organise and facilitate a co-design scenario workshop at a landscape level (i.e., a watershed or municipality in the Philippines) for the purposes of the CITIZEN-SDSS project. The four landscape-level workshops are followed by two regional-level workshops, which build on the outcomes of the former and, in principle, follow a similar sequence. Co-design workshops, which are a form of participatory land-use planning, can help to catalyse stakeholder engagement and improve governance in rural landscapes (Do et al., 2021). Conversely, a lack of participation and acknowledgement of customary land-use practices can inhibit the successful implementation of current and future land-use plans, policies, and regulations aimed at sustaining ecosystem services and biodiversity in the long term. In many countries, conventional, centralised, top-down land-use planning approaches have been widely practised with limited success due to a lack of flexibility in adapting to local circumstances (Bourgoin et al., 2012; Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2010). For the purposes of the CITIZEN-SDSS project, the participatory co-design workshops draw on components of the 'Land-Use Planning for Multiple Ecosystem Services' (LUMES) framework (Dewi et al., 2015), as well as other forms of participatory appraisal (Bodin et al., 2011; Hauck et al., 2016; Lippe et al., 2011; Lippe et al., 2017). Research ethics review and safeguards for data protection and confidentiality are applied, including free, prior and informed consent (FPIC), during all phases of co-design and stakeholder-related interactions.

The default LUMES framework has been adapted to meet the needs of CITIZEN-SDSS. This includes the following main steps: (i) compilation of current local and regional land-use issues and perspectives on current land-use plans; (ii) participatory development of baseline, local and regional scenarios, with the latter adopting future land-use interventions preferred by local or regional stakeholders; (iii) assessment of the impact of the developed scenarios on the ecosystem services of the landscape using a spatiotemporal modelling framework. This framework is used to explore potential trade-offs, conflicting demands and synergies of current and future land and resource uses together with stakeholders. Back casting exercises are used to set targets for the future landscape and propose interventions to achieve them (van Asselt et al., 2010). After agreeing on common goals, workshop participants are split into Barangay and Municipality groups to formulate a future scenario, including the interventions, the location of each intervention, the actors involved, and the policy support needed for the

interventions. Land-use maps and other materials are provided to stimulate group discussion. Participants are informed that the impacts of the suggested interventions are evaluated after the workshop using a spatiotemporal modelling framework (project phase 3). The modelling results are presented at feedback consultations and workshops (project phase 4) to discuss lessons learned and the implications for long-term environmental and land use planning in the local or regional context, respectively.

2.1 Purpose and general features

The overall aim of the co-design workshops is to develop local and regional narratives of future land use patterns and scenarios based on interventions defined by participating stakeholders. Documenting the co-design process and the actions of certain stakeholders during the participatory workshops allows for an in-depth analysis of the type of information or knowledge product (e.g., maps, qualitative or quantitative indicators or visuals) that stakeholders perceive as useful for future land use planning. This concept of knowledge products is lacking in many co-design settings and is often neglected by government agencies when conducting land use planning workshops. The workshops follow FPIC principles and are organised as two-day events in the four study landscapes and as one-day events at the regional level in the study regions of Eastern Visayas and Cagayan Valley. Participants comprise 10–20 stakeholders at the landscape level and 5–10 stakeholders at the regional level. Those participating at the landscape level will be divided into barangay and municipality-level sub-groups (see **section 2.3** below for further details). Subsequently, the total number of co-design workshops refers to $n=6$, with 1 per study landscape: Balasig watershed, Penablanca Municipality, Maasin City, Silago Municipality ($n=4$), and 1 per study region: Southern Leyte, and the parts of Southern Cagayan Province and Northern Isabela Province – stretching from the Municipalities of Penablanca and Tumauini ($n=2$).

2.2 Specific objectives

- Co-creating future land use scenarios reflecting diverse stakeholder visions.
- Assessing ecosystem services (ES) trade-offs and synergies under different scenario settings.
- Identifying areas for nature-based solutions (NBS) as priority intervention zones (e.g., mangrove rehabilitation, agroforestry buffers, riparian restoration) that can deliver the largest ES gains and climate-resilience co-benefits.
- Building consensus on a shortlist of NBS interventions for integration into the Municipal Environment and Natural Resources Office (MENRO) work plan and the comprehensive land use plan (CLUP) revisions.
- Using back casting exercises to set specific, actionable landscape and ES targets for 2040, and outline interventions in how to reach them.

2.3 Scope of target participants at landscape-level

- Local government officials (e.g., municipality planning, environment and natural resources, agriculture, disaster and risk management),
- Barangay captain and representatives,
- Not considered: Local farmers and villagers (Barangay captains serve as proxy in this case), Youth and Women group leaders.

Table 1: Summary of target stakeholder groups, suggested representation and rationale of participation

Stakeholder group	Suggested representatives	Why essential
LGU	Mayor's planning team, MENRO, MPDO, MDRRMO, DRRMO	Policy alignment & budget leverage
Barangay captain and representatives	For each study Barangay ($n=6$ in total per landscape)	Place-based insights, legitimacy

3 Organizational matters

3.1 Venue setting

A venue such as a conference room or lecture hall is required that can host 15 to 30 participants, including the workshop team. The venue must be equipped with a HiFi sound system, microphones, WiFi access, sufficient number of tables, chairs and further offering the opportunity for catering, coffee and snacks.

3.2 Workshop materials

Projector or TV screen, workshop kit for each participant (workshop program, name tag, A4 colored map printouts, booklet or paper sheets to take notes), sheet attendance list, sheet written consent of each participant to confirm (or not) that workshop is recorded (video and audio) and to be used for internal project purposes, homepage and social media, manila paper, tape roll, color markers, meta-cards, pens (see for details session description below), color printer for ad hoc printing needs.

Moreover, colored map printouts (n=7) are provided as means of discussion in sites A1 (1x per study area to be shown as wallpaper), A3 (2x per study area) and A4 (n=15 as part of individual participant workshop kit) with the following themes (i-iv builds on: Asare and Lippe 2025; v-vii: builds on: Asare et al. 2025):

- i. satellite image study landscape with barangay names and boundaries, major roads and rivers,
- ii. overview of study landscape with barangay names and boundaries, major roads and rivers, and tenurial instruments (e.g., CBFMA, and others according to DENR and LGU data),
- iii. land cover 2020 according to NAMRIA (2020),
- iv. forest cover changes (undisturbed forest, deforestation, disturbed forests, forest regrowth) in 2024 according to JRC/ TMF,
- v. composite ecosystem service index (CESI), highlighting areas with high and low ecosystem service potentials,
- vi. land degradation sensitivity index (LDSI), highlighting areas with high and low land degradation risk potentials,
- vii. cold-/hotspots for nature-based solutions.

3.3 Team composition

The workshop is ideally composed of:

- **1 facilitator** who is able to speak Filipino, and if possible relevant local dialects (Cebuano, Ilocano, Ibanag). This person will be the focal point during the workshop and is introducing session objectives, assignments/ tasks to participants, and helps to facilitate the discussions. He/she is supported by the other workshop team members.
- **1 moderator** who are able to speak Tagalog, and if possible relevant local dialects (Cebuano, Ilocano, Ibanag), to support the facilitator in guiding the discussions and engaging with participants during individual sessions.
- **1 team member** responsible for documentation, to ensure that all expected outcomes are collected, documented appropriately, and are complete using a checklist. The main task is to crosscheck the expected outcomes with the produced workshop results, to remind the facilitator about missing outcomes if needed, and storing all output products appropriately.
- **1 team member** responsible for documenting the workshop activities using digital camera and microphone.

4 Workshop day 1

Total duration: 9am to 4pm; with 5 hours of workshop activities and PPTs

4.1 Opening session

Duration: 60 min

Materials required: Projector or TV Screen, workshop kit for each participant (workshop program, name tag, A4 colored map printouts, etc.), written consent of each participant to confirm (or not) that workshop is recorded (video and audio) and to be used for internal project purposes, homepage and social media.

Objectives: General introduction of CITIZEN-SDSS project and related workshop objectives.

The session is divided in 3 sections:

- **National Anthem/Prayer, Welcome and opening remarks, Ice-breaker/ Energizer (20 min)**
- **PowerPoint (PPT) presentation** describing workshop objectives, purpose and approach on future land use scenario planning, and outlining agenda of day 1 and day 2 **(10 min)**
- **PPT and QA** to remind on concepts of ecosystem services (ES), land degradation (LD), nature-based solutions (NBS) **(30 min)**

4.2 Session: Context setting and presentation of MCA results

Duration: 60 min

Materials required: 20 pens, 100 meta cards, TV Screen or projector to show high resolution satellite images and maps, colored map printouts (n=7) 1x in A1, 20x scoring sheet in A4 provided to each participant.

Objectives: Setting the scene by presenting findings of key information per study area and MCA maps.

The session is divided in 3 sections:

- 1) **PowerPoint (PPT) presentation** on currently prevailing land cover types (NAMRIA) and changes (2010-2020), forest change dynamics (2000-2024), perceived ecosystem service supply hotspots (CESI) and land degradation risk areas (LDSI), cold-/hotspots for nature-based solutions (NBS) per study landscape, summary of CLUP aspirations **(30 min)**.
- 2) **Group discussion:** Building on PPT, participants discuss key challenges and opportunities on present land uses and forest change dynamics, ecosystem service supply hotspots (CESI), land degradation sensitivity/ risk areas (LDSI), cold-/hotspots for nature-based solutions (NBS) per study landscape **(20 min)**.
 - **Expected outcomes:**
 - i. General understanding of participants on present land use and forest change dynamics, ecosystem service supply hotspots (CESI), land degradation sensitivity/ risk areas (LDSI), cold-/hotspots for nature-based solutions (NBS) per study landscape.
 - ii. Group discussion recorded by digital camera, and relevant notes taken.
- 3) **Map evaluation:** Participant score (1-disagree, 2-neutral, 3-agree) their comprehension of the CESI, LDSI and NBS maps using a provided A4 evaluation sheet. In case of disagreement, participants write short explanations on the evaluation sheet **(10 min)**.

- **Expected outcomes**
 - i. Per participant, 1 evaluation sheet on presented CESI, LDSI, NBS maps completed.

4.3 Session: Co-creation and scenario development

Total duration: 120 to 180 min

4.3.1 Present and future causes/ drivers of land use change

Duration: 60 to 90 min

Materials required: 10 markers, 50 meta cards, 2 tape rolls, 8 manila paper sheets, TV screen or projector to show high resolution satellite images and maps, colored map printouts (n=7) 1x in A1 and 2x in A3, 2x Future Driver Indicator sheet for Group 1 and Group 2 prepared according to Table 2 format.

Objectives:

- 1) Participants reflect and if needed expand the list of present drivers of land use change presented to them as part of the MCA findings;
- 2) Identify, assess and rank future drivers of land use change. Participants are split into 2 groups, with **Group 1** referring to the municipality level (including all technical experts/ staff from LGU, representatives from DENR incl. CENRO and PASU), while **Group 2** refer to the barangay level (including Barangay captains, and other relevant B-LGU officials if applicable, and representatives of PO).

Note: In case of CITIZEN-SDSS, six study Barangays were purposively chosen for fieldwork activities (household questionnaires, ground truthing, forest/ agroforestry/ timber plantation inventories) with always two of them referring to a particular cropland/ forest area Barangay pair (see **Table 1** for details). This may create challenges for the Barangay participants (Group 2) trying to find consensus among diverse context settings during a certain group activity. To overcome this, and to ensure that all voices are heard, the particular Barangay should be indicated on each card when reporting as Group 2.

Table 2: Overview of Barangay pair of study landscapes based on cropland/ forest land cover area NAMRIA

Barangay pair – HHQ	Balasisg	Penablanca	Silago	Maasin
CROPLAND (CL) , “have cropland area but no forest area per total Brgy. area”	Union (Cabagan) Pilig Alto (Cabagan)	Dodan Cabbo	Sap-ang Sudmon	Bactul I Hantag
CROP-FORESTLAND (CFL) , “have more cropland area than forest area per total Brgy. area”	Camasi (Tumauini) Cumabao (Tumauini)	Callao Nanguilatan	Tuba-on Salvacion	Baugo San Jose
FOREST-CROPLAND (FOCL) , “have more forest area than cropland area per total Brgy. area”	Masipi East (Cabagan) Dy Abra (Tumauini)	Buyun Minanga	Catmon Katipunan	Cagnituan Lunas

Based on NAMRIA 2020 land cover map; see for further details: Asare and Lippe (2025).

The session is divided into 3 sections:

- 1) **PPT presenting i.) influencing causes/ drivers of of land use change** grouped into the categories ‘direct’ (**forest products extraction:** illegal logging/ timber poaching, charcoal making, fuelwood

gathering, NTFP gathering; **agricultural expansion**: kaingin, conversion of forests, grazing, horticulture or orchards; **infrastructure expansion**: settlement expansion, road construction, mining, tourism facilities, hydropower/ dam/ irrigation construction; **biophysical/ natural factors**: climate change, typhoons, floods, landslides, forest/ brush/ grassland fire, and 'indirect' (regulations and governance, socio-demographic, economic-market-technological), and ii.) **identified land degradation** examples degradation as mentioned during MCA interviews (10 min).

- 2) **Group activity 1: "Reflect on current causes/ drivers of land use change"**: Each group discuss and reflect on given PPT list and use it as reference to list out current **direct and indirect causes/ factors** of land use change per study landscape or barangay. Identified **causes/ factors** are written on cards and stuck on manila paper for each group (20 min).

Guiding question 1: *What are current causes/ drivers of land use change at landscape (=municipality or watershed) or at barangay-level?*

- **Expected outputs:** Group 1 and 2 reflect on current drivers (direct, indirect), and confirm or expand provided KII lists by writing drivers on cards. In case of Group 2 (Barangay-level), participants need to identify common 'overarching' drivers, and drivers unique for their Barangay. Each group sticks cards on manila paper, documented by digital photos.
- 3) **Group activity 2: "Identify, assess and rank future causes/ drivers of land use change"**: Each group discuss and reflect on group activity 1 outputs, and use it as reference to list potential **direct and indirect causes/ drivers** of future land use change per study area or barangay. Each driver is assessed according to their level of importance on influencing future land use change based on three indicators: **duration, total land area, impact on ecosystem services (Table 2)**. Furthermore, each **future cause/ driver** is ranked (high, medium, low) on their overall importance, and a percentage (%) has to be attributed to each future cause/ driver, totalling 100% to all scored driver cards. Identified and assessed future causes/ drivers (direct, indirect), and ranking scores are written on cards and stuck on manila paper using the layout format of **Table 3**.

Table 3: Scoring approach of perceived potential future causes/ factors of land use change

Duration	1= short-term (1 to 10 years) 2= mid-term (10 to 25 years) 3= long-term (longer than 25 years)
Influence on total land area (Municipality/ Watershed or Barangay)	1= Less than 10% 2=Between 10-25% 3= Between 25-50% 4= More than 50%
Impact on ecosystem services (ES)	1=Negative 2=Neutral 3=Positive

Note: Prepare 1 manila paper with Table inputs as reference for participant groups during session

Guiding question 2a: *What will be the most important future causes/ drivers (direct, indirect) of land use change at municipality/ watershed or barangay-level?*

Guiding questions 2b:

- *What will be future causes/ drivers (direct, indirect) duration during a period of 1 to more than 25 years?*

- What will be future causes/ drivers influence on total land area (per Barangay or study area)?
- How will future causes/ drivers impact ecosystem services in the considered timeframe?

Table 4: Future cause/driver Indicator sheet to assess their duration, influence on land area, impact on ES

Future cause/driver	Category (direct, indirect)	Duration	Land Area	Impact on ES	Ranking of importance (high, medium, low)	Ranking in percentage (= 100% in total)
D 1: Add Card						
D 2: Add Card						
D 3: Add Card						
D 4: Add Card						
D 5: Add Card						
Etc.						

Note 1: Table should be already prepared on manila paper (2x) before workshop for group 1 and group 2.

Note 2: Direct cause/ driver: Forest products extraction, Agricultural expansion, Infrastructure expansion, Biophysical/ Natural factors; **Indirect cause/ driver:** Demography (e.g., population growth, migration), economic (e.g., crop-market prices), governance (regulations, development projects), innovations (e.g., new seed hybrids, fertilizers, machinery use).

- **Expected outputs 1:** Group 1 and 2 reflect on current and potential future causes/ drivers, (direct, indirect) of land use change using the provided KII list shown on a PPT as discussion basis, and writing each considered cause/ driver on a separate card;
- **Expected output 2:** For each future cause/ driver card, three impact indicators (duration, land area, impact ES) need to be described, assessed according to **Table 2**, and ranked according to level of importance and in percentage. Written cards are stucked on future cause/ driver indicator sheet prepared as manila paper for each group (see **Table 3**);
- **Group activity 2 results are presented to all participants. Each group has to name a speaker. Presentation is recorded by digital camera.**

4.3.2 Co-designing scenarios of future land use change

Duration: 60 to 90 min

Materials required: 10x Markers, 50x Cards, 2x Tape roll, 8x Manila paper, TV Screen or projector to show high resolution satellite images and maps, colored map printouts (n=7) 1x in A1 and 2x in A3, summary of CLUP vision and background information on population growth, land use cover per landscape and target barangay, land use change rates according to NAMRIA for 2003-2020, forest change rates according to satellite analysis for 2000 to 2024.

Objectives: Participant develop 3 scenario storylines of future land use change (conservation-/ development-oriented, hybrid as balance of conservation and development scenario) they consider plausible to happen under certain circumstances and interventions. Participants are split into two groups: Group 1 = municipality level, Group 2 = barangay level (see for details page 3).

Scenario types to be designed refer to:

- **Conservation-oriented scenario** (titled as e.g., “Conservation Paradise”) that may ensure forest conservation, the expansion of nature-based solutions, river bank protection, and preservation of important ecosystem services at Barangay and/ or municipality-/ watershed-level;
- **Development-oriented scenario** (titled as e.g., “Development first”) that supports local livelihood upgrades by e.g., improved farming activities, outmigration, off-farm working opportunities etc.;
- **Hybrid scenario** (titled as e.g., “Pro Development NBS”) that seeks to balance between conservation-oriented and development-oriented goals, and considers nature-based solutions (NBS) at landscape-level.

The session is divided into 2 sections:

- 1) **Short PPT on purpose of scenario development**, with providing further brief explanations how scenario storylines/ narratives will be assessed by using GIS models during 2025 to 2026 (project phase 3), and results being presented during a feedback consolidation phase during 2026 (project phase 4);
- 2) **Group activity 3 and presentation of group activities to all participants. Presentation is recorded by digital camera.**

Group activity 3: Each group develop 3 scenario storylines of future land use change (conservation-oriented, development-oriented, hybrid to balance conservation & development goals at landscape-level) they consider plausible to happen under certain circumstances and interventions. Focus should be given geographically to the municipality or Barangay-level.

Guiding question 3: “How will the future landscape in case of your municipality or Barangay look like in 2045?”

The development of each scenario is based on the future land use change causes/ driver task (**Group activity 2**) and take into account expected future socio-demographic, economic, environmental conditions, as well as government regulations and interventions. The developed scenarios will be assessed using GIS and modelling tools (after the completion of the workshops – project phase 3). Results will be presented during feedback workshops as part of a multi-stakeholder consolidation (project phase 4) in 2026.

Scenario storylines can consider the current CLUP/ LCAP plans and their stipulated goals and visions per study area/ landscape, or other background information such as population growth rates, land cover composition according to NAMRIA, forest type change according to satellite analysis, etc. This background information is provided on summary sheets as part of each participant’s workshop kit.

A scenario can simply refer to the continuation of the present land use (change) trends, e.g., agricultural areas are expanding by Kainign in forests areas due to high market prices for corn/ coconut, etc. It could also refer to expected land use changes, e.g., expansion of NGPs areas caused by government programs, changes in livelihood conditions, infrastructure projects, or by increasing climate change calamities such as typhoons, flooding events, drought spells, etc.

Table 5: Summary scenario types and storyline of Group 1 (Municipality) and Group 2 (Barangay-level)

Scenario type	Group 1: Municipality	Group 2: Barangay-level
Conservation-oriented	<i>Short description (e.g., 50-100 words) of scenario as narrative or storyline (can be done in Filipino)</i>	
Development-oriented		
Hybrid to balance conservation & development goals		

Note: Table should be prepared as manila paper (2x) prior the commencement of Group Activity 4.

- **Expected outputs:** Scenario narratives / storyline descriptions of each scenario written on sheets and manila paper, documented by digital photos.
- **Group activity 3 results are presented to all participants** and discuss pros and cons of its likely future occurrence. **Each group has to name a speaker. Presentation is recorded by digital camera.**

4.4 Reflection day 1 and outlook day 2

Duration: 15-30 min

- General feedback of participants on workshop content, timing, comprehension of technical details
- 1 slide PPT as outlook on agenda day 2

5 Workshop day 2

Total duration: 9am - 3pm; with 4 hours of workshop activities and PPTs

5.1 Opening Session

Duration: 30 min

Materials required: Projector or TV Screen, Workshop kit for each participant (workshop program, name tag, A4 colored map printouts).

Objectives: Introducing day 2 objectives and agenda

The session is divided in 2 sections:

- **Welcome and Energizer (15 min)**
- **PowerPoint (PPT) presentation** introducing day 2 agenda **(5 min)**

5.2 Session: Mapping future areas of change

Duration: 60 to 90 min

Materials required: Projector or TV screen, Workshop kit for each participant (workshop program, name tag, A4 colored map printouts), A3 color print outs (6 to 7) of study Barangays and study Municipality/ Watershed, 20 acetate sheets in A2 to A3 size, 50 Cards, 2x Tape roll, 4x Manila paper, 3D icons, carton chips.

Objectives: Participant groups use the developed scenario storyline “hybrid” to identify expected future areas of land use change (hot-/coldspot), areas prone for increasing land degradation (hot-/coldspot), and potential areas for Nature-based Solutions, including the identification of a particular NBS intervention using the A3 map color printouts (e.g., admin boundaries + tenurial instruments) as background and geographical/spatial reference, overlaid by acetate sheets **with marked areas of change**. Participants are split into two groups: **Group 1** = municipality level, **Group 2** = barangay level (see for details: page 3).

The session is divided into 2 sections:

- 1) **Short PPT to introduce task and purpose of mapping out future areas of change, land degradation, and NBS intervention zones (hot-/coldspot).** One slide providing brief explanations on how scenario storylines/ narratives will be assessed after the completion of the co-design scenario workshops using GIS-based models during 2025 to 2026, and that results are being presented during a feedback consolidation phase in 2026;
- 2) **Group activity 4 and presentation of individual group outcome to all participants. Presentation is recorded by digital camera.**

Guiding question 4: “*Where do you expect future land use change to occur in case of scenario “hybrid” for your municipality or Barangay by 2045?*”

Group activity 4: Participants use the developed scenario storyline “hybrid” to map out expected future areas of land use change (hot-/coldspots), areas prone for increasing land degradation (hot-/coldspots), and potential areas for Nature-based Solutions including the identification of a particular NBS intervention, using the A3 map color printouts (e.g., admin boundaries + tenurial instruments) as background and geographical/spatial reference.

For this purpose, acetate sheets are overlaid on the provided A3 map printouts, given to participants, laid on table. Participants use color markers to identify on the acetate sheets future areas of land use change (hot-/coldspot), areas prone for increasing land degradation (hot-/coldspot), and potential areas for Nature-

based Solutions. The latter has to include the description of the chosen NBS intervention which can be either written on the acetate sheet directly or on separate card instead.

Further provided 3D icons that e.g., resemble crop types, houses, etc., and carton chips are offered to each group as other means to visualize the future changes and its drivers/ factors on the colored map printouts, respectively the acetate sheets.

A legend has to be written separately on card(s) to explain certain map features and the purpose of a 3D icon or carton chip. This must include background information on certain assumptions, land use change rates that can help readers later to understand the mapped features, areas of change, and identified NBS priority zones.

Digital photos are taken to document all produced map features, with at least 1 digital photo taken from a birds-eye view to enabling the digitalization of drawn map features in a GIS software such as QGIS.

- **Expected outputs:** Narratives / storyline description “hybrid” mapped out for each scenario on acetate sheets, overlaid on A3 color map printouts. Legends and further explanations on map features, purpose and use of 3D icons and carton chips are written on cards. Mapped scenario “hybrid” is documented by digital photos of all produced map features, with at least 1 digital photo taken from a birds-eye view to enabling the digitalization of drawn map features in a GIS software.
- **Group activity 4 outcomes are presented to all participants in afternoon session (after lunch break)** and discuss pros and cons of its likely future occurrence.
- **Each group has to name a speaker. Presentation is recorded by digital camera.**

5.3 Session: Back casting intervention pathway(s)

Duration: 60 to 90 min

Materials required: Projector or TV screen, Workshop kit for each participant (workshop program, name tag, A4 colored map printouts), A3 color print outs (6 to 7) of study Barangays and study Municipality/ Watershed, 50 Cards, 2x Tape roll, 4x Manila paper.

Objectives: Participant groups develop intervention pathways for scenario “hybrid” by describing required activities (short-, mid-, long-term), and responsible actors for the successful implementation of the scenario.

The session is divided into 2 sections:

- 1) **Short PPT to introduce task and purpose of back casting exercise;**
- 2) **Group activity 5 and presentation of individual group outcome to all participants. Presentation is recorded by digital camera.**

Guiding question 5: *“What are the requirements for scenario “hybrid” to be achieved in case of your municipality or Barangay by 2045?”*

Group activity 5: Participants use the developed scenario storyline “hybrid” to describe intervention pathways and actions that need to be achieved and/ or sustained, at short-term (1 to 10 years), mid-term (10 to 25 years), long-term (longer than 25 years) time horizons. Outcomes are document and written on a manila paper using the layout shown in **Table 5**. Responsible actors need to identified for each activity or intervention and per time horizon. Cards can be additionally used to describe further actions, interventions and responsible actors in more detail.

Table 6: Layout back casting for hybrid scenario to describe actions and responsible actors per time horizon

Scenario	Time horizon		
	Short-term (1 to 10 years)	Mid-term (10 to 25 years)	Long-term (Longer than 25 years)
Hybrid	Actions/ Interventions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X • Y • Z Responsible actors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X • Y • Z 	Actions/ Interventions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X • Y • Z Responsible actors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X • Y • Z 	Actions/ Interventions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X • Y • Z Responsible actors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X • Y • Z

Note: Table should be prepared as manila paper (2x) prior the commencement of Group Activity 5.

- **Expected outputs:** Completed Table 5 for Group 1 and Group 2 on manila paper.
- **Group activity 5 results are presented to all participants in afternoon session (after lunch break).** Pros and cons of scenario “hybrid” likely future occurrence **shall be discussed and reflected.**
- **Each group has to name a speaker. Group voting is document on card. Presentation is recorded by digital camera.**

5.4 Session: Group presentations of mapping and back casting activities

Duration: 60 min

Materials required: Projector or TV screen, Results of Group Activity 4 and 5; Workshop evaluation sheet.

Objectives: Participant group 1 and 2 present outcomes of group activity 4 and 5 for Barangay- and Watershed/ Municipality-level. Altogether, participants discuss lessons learned for present and future land use planning and environmental management activities at municipality/ watershed-, or Barangay-level.

The session is concluded by a short evaluation of workshop activities, timing, comprehension of given PowerPoint presentations and provided materials. Each participant submits a provided A4 workshop evaluation sheet for this purpose.

The session is divided into 2 sections:

- 1) **Presentations (4x in total, 10 min each) of group activities 4 and 5 for Barangay- and Watershed/ Municipality-level (40 min).**
- 2) **Participants discuss developed scenario narrative “hybrid” at Barangay- and Watershed/ Municipality-level (20 min).**

Expected outcomes:

- **Recorded presentations of morning session activities (4 and 5) for Barangay- and Watershed/ Municipality-level recorded by digital camera.**
- **Workshop evaluation sheet is completed by each participant and collected.**

5.5 Closing program

Duration: 30 to 45 min

- Outlook on CITIZEN-SDSS Phase 3 and 4 activities in 2025 and 2026

6 References

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